

Vibranium Bridge:

Democratising access to strategic consulting through generative AI

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Authors:

Shawn Ford (Vibranium Bridge)
Stuart Gillespie (Independent Contractor)
Giulia Tomba (The Alan Turing Institute)

Additional Contributors:

Arielle Bennett (The Alan Turing Institute)
Léllé Demertzi (The Alan Turing Institute)

Topic overview

This case study explores how **Vibranium Bridge**, an AI strategy and digital transformation consultancy, is democratising access to board-level advisory services. Utilising founder Shawn Ford's extensive experience in management consulting and senior corporate leadership roles, the company is developing an AI Integration Suite designed to augment traditional consultancy by embedding tested strategic frameworks and proprietary expertise into a chatbot-style AI system, while maintaining human oversight and robust cyber security and governance practices. Participation in The Turing Way Practitioners Hub has supported this work by enhancing Shawn's knowledge and thinking in areas including cyber security, data readiness, AI roadmap development, and responsible human-AI collaboration.

Expanding access to strategic expertise

Strategic consulting is – for the most part – expensive and resource-intensive. Boutique consulting firms often deploy teams of experienced professionals over weeks or months to diagnose organisational issues, design transformation programmes, and guide implementation. For many businesses, the cost and time commitment can be prohibitive.

Shawn Ford founded Vibranium Bridge – named after the super-strong metal from the Marvel Universe – to address this accessibility gap. With a background that includes senior roles at PwC and Amazon, he has worked on large-scale infrastructure and transformation programmes. And, as generative AI emerged, he invested time in education and upskilling, completing several online courses run by Stanford University to deepen his understanding of machine learning and AI applications.

Throughout his career, Shawn observed that many organisations – particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) – lack access to high-quality strategic advice. AI, he believed, could provide a solution. Shawn says: “If you look at traditional consulting, you might have three people working for six weeks at a cost of hundreds of thousands, just to deliver insight. That model simply isn’t accessible for most smaller organisations. Our ambition is to give companies with more limited resources access to the same depth and rigour of ‘best in class’ strategic consulting by using AI to reduce cost and expand reach.”

An AI system built on top-class consulting knowledge

Vibranium Bridge’s core offering alongside traditional consulting is its AI Integration Suite: a system of ‘digital colleagues’ designed to support organisations across strategic and operational functions. While the suite already includes features such as automated customer enquiry response (designed to free up clients’ employees to focus on higher-value work), the company is now developing the consulting and advisory aspect of its AI-assisted offering.

Shawn’s vision is to democratise access to board-level advice by embedding best practice consulting frameworks – drawn from his own knowledge and experience – into a configurable AI system. He has sought to codify approaches to aspects such as strategic diagnosis, transformation roadmapping, revenue growth strategy, governance and board-level decision support, and digital and AI transformation planning. These frameworks and question sets are typically accessible only through expensive consultancy engagements, whereas Vibranium Bridge proposes to offer this expertise through on-demand generative AI.

Shawn notes that general-purpose AI tools would not naturally generate responses to input prompts from customers that reflect established consulting practice or provide the required depth of advice. They would also be more likely to hallucinate or produce inaccurate responses. His goal in developing Vibranium Bridge’s bespoke system is therefore to harness the speed and efficiency of AI techniques without compromising on rigour of reasoning or output.

Configuring AI to reflect organisational 'DNA'

A distinctive feature of Vibranium Bridge's AI system is its behavioural framework. Developed in collaboration with a specialist software partner in Texas, the backend system is structured around ten foundational 'codes' that shape how the AI behaves. Through a user interface similar to ChatGPT on the front end, organisations can define their mission, values and communication style – and refine them over time. Behind the scenes, the system interprets these inputs to ensure responses align with the organisation's 'DNA'. Whether a client operates in pharmaceuticals or plumbing, responses appropriately reflect the sector.

Shawn compares the process to training a new employee to embody a company's tone and norms: for example, an AI customer service agent may be instructed to refer to "booking an appointment" with a potential client rather than "generating a lead", balancing accuracy with empathy and jargon-free language. This refinement through prompting, says Shawn, is akin to adding paintwork and furnishings to the underlying building structure provided by the ten codes. Additionally, the Texas-based technical team regularly releases upgraded versions of the system to enhance its robustness and response quality. In testing, these updates have improved how human-like and context-aware the responses are.

Human-in-the-loop and other considerations

Despite the sophistication of the AI layer, Shawn is clear that the system is not intended to replace human judgement – particularly at board or executive level. For important decisions or actions, users of the consultancy service are encouraged via a disclaimer to validate outputs with Vibranium Bridge's human advisors. "You can use AI as a powerful first point of call," says Shawn, "but ultimately there are moments where human accountability and judgement are essential."

He adds: "AI is our key differentiator in the market. But that comes with a responsibility to ensure areas like cyber security, data privacy and governance controls are up to scratch." Being a Practitioners Hub Expert-in-Residence has helped Shawn explore these areas and strengthen his knowledge: he highlights the cyber security elements of the programme as particularly influential, prompting detailed discussions with his technical partner to ensure that the system is robust enough to maintain the trust of clients who may be sharing important or sensitive data. "In the consulting sector, trust is everything," says Shawn. "We also use practical measures such as access controls, data encryption, model input and output logging, and clear protocols for how client data is handled, stored and deleted."

Shawn also found the Practitioners Hub sessions on strategy and roadmap development valuable, allowing him to build on and share his experiences at PwC and Amazon – particularly around stakeholder engagement and leadership buy-in. Discussions on data readiness, meanwhile, reinforced the importance of understanding the underlying data before layering AI solutions on top.

Challenges: Establishing a foothold in a traditional industry

With traditional consulting often being built on longstanding personal relationships and reputation, gaining traction in the industry can be a challenge for a new company (or a company offering new technology). Introducing an AI-augmented advisory model into that traditional environment inevitably raises questions such as whether an AI system can replicate the judgement, nuance, and discretion expected at board level. Shawn recognises that impressive technology alone does not open doors – credibility does. His strategy has therefore been to leverage his existing consulting background and industry experience as the foundation, using the company's AI Integration Suite as a demonstrable extension of this experience.

Linked to trust are issues of accuracy and accessibility. Vibranium Bridge's stated aim is to democratise strategy consulting, but translating tailored, contextual advisory services into a scalable AI model requires careful handling and an acknowledgement that working with AI in this way carries risks, including outputs that are inaccurate or not specific enough to be useful (no AI system will provide 100% accuracy, notes Shawn). Shawn addresses this by grounding the system in extensive proprietary documentation and tested methodologies – a time-consuming but necessary task – while retaining a human-in-the-loop safeguard for critical decisions. The platform's subscription-based model is designed to lower the cost barrier without removing the option for direct human consultation where the situation demands it.

It is also worth noting here that client expectations can vary considerably. Smaller organisations, in Shawn's experience, often seek a straightforward AI solution that delivers immediate operational value with minimal configuration. Larger businesses, by contrast, tend to have the freedom and resources to experiment more broadly and are likely to see greater benefits from the AI-assisted consulting model in particular – even to the extent of wanting to offer the tool to their own customers once they become aware of the productivity benefits.

Next steps: Securing clients and demonstrating effectiveness

With controlled testing having proved successful, Vibranium Bridge is now focused on securing and delivering client contracts for the AI Integration Suite (and in particular the AI-assisted consultancy tool). Because the strength of the system lies in the quality of its embedded frameworks, ongoing curation and refinement of this documentation is central to its development.

Technical development of the system will also continue, including efforts to improve interoperability with existing organisational platforms, to ensure robust cyber security and governance safeguards, and to refine the configuration features that allow the system to reflect an organisation's voice and operating model.

Longer-term, Shawn aims to demonstrate clearly within the sector that AI-powered advisory systems can act as a responsible and effective first point of call for organisations seeking high-quality consulting services but without the budget to appoint a big-name firm – and to show how AI can be implemented responsibly and in line with best practices.

Reflections on *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub

“The Practitioners Hub has been incredibly valuable. It reinforced how critical it is to get the governance and data foundations right for an AI solution. The sessions on cyber security, IP and AI roadmapping were particularly useful – you’re unlikely to get this type of breadth and depth anywhere else. My fellow Experts-in-Residence have been genuinely entrepreneurial and curious, which helps you see not only the challenges of today but the opportunities of tomorrow. There are always small nuggets of insight you take away from conversations: it fills gaps in your knowledge and gives you the confidence to go out and speak to stakeholders about AI in a more authoritative way. You could say it’s a cure for impostor syndrome.”

Shawn Ford,
Founder of Vibranium Bridge

Key takeaways

- AI can lower the cost barrier to high-quality strategic consulting, expanding access for companies with fewer resources.
- Frameworks based on existing knowledge and experience can be embedded into AI systems to provide quick, context-aware advisory support – complemented by prompt engineering to instill a company voice and ‘DNA’.
- Human-AI collaboration is essential: AI augments rather than replaces the judgement of experienced consultants or executives, and takes into account the fallibility of AI outputs even in the best-engineered systems. And trust and relationship-building remain critical in professional services – even in relation to AI-augmented approaches.
- Cyber security and data readiness are among the key foundations of responsible AI deployment. Working with a trusted external technical partner can help address these areas.
- AI systems require continuous review of outputs, controls and governance processes, rather than a ‘set and forget’ approach. Building in regular evaluation loops helps maintain quality and manage risk over time.

Contributors and acknowledgements

This case study is published under *The Turing Way Practitioners* Hub 2025–26 Cohort – case study series. The Practitioners Hub is *The Turing Way* project that works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2025, The Turing Way team welcomed **Shawn Ford from Vibranium Bridge**, as Expert-in-Residence to discuss and share their implementation approaches to data science and AI as well as build additional skills around best practices in responsible, ethical, and collaborative working. We thank them for leading the development of this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioner’s Hub was supported by Innovate UK BridgeAI from 2023–2026. BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. The programme bridges the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency, and data privacy, BridgeAI aims to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

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The Turing Way Practitioners Hub’s 2025–26 Cohort was co-delivered by **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher – Open Source Practices and Dr Ann Borda, Senior Research Community Manager. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical writer for this case study, and others in the series. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager. **Giulia Tomba** is the Case Study Liaison for this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Malvika Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of ‘Experts in Residence’ across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: theturingway@gmail.com

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